

TYPES OF MODERN TECHNOLOGIES AND THEIR APPLICATION IN MOLECULAR PHYSICS EDUCATION

A.Z. Jalolova

Shahrisabz State Pedagogical Institute, Phd Student

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Abstract. *The rapid development of modern information and communication technologies necessitates the improvement of teaching methods for natural sciences, particularly molecular physics, in higher education. The abstract nature of molecular-level processes makes them difficult to understand using traditional teaching approaches.*

The aim of this study is to identify types of modern educational technologies and to develop effective ways of applying them in teaching molecular physics.

The study employs analysis and synthesis methods, pedagogical experiments, comparative analysis, as well as virtual laboratories, computer simulations, and interactive educational platforms. Classes were modeled using modern technologies, and their effectiveness was evaluated.

The results demonstrate that classes organized using modern technologies enhance students' understanding of learning materials, enable visualization of abstract concepts, and promote the development of independent and critical thinking skills.

The application of modern technologies in molecular physics education significantly improves the effectiveness of the learning process and the quality of education. The findings are of practical importance for improving the methodology of teaching molecular physics in higher education institutions.

Keywords: *modern educational technologies, molecular physics, virtual laboratories, computer simulations, interactive learning, digital learning environments, physics teaching methodology, learning effectiveness.*

INTRODUCTION

Nowadays, improving the quality of education in the higher education system and introducing innovative approaches to teaching subjects are one of the pressing issues. In particular, the complexity and abstractness of molecular physics leads to its insufficient mastery by students in the traditional teaching process. Therefore, the use of modern technologies in molecular physics education is an important factor in increasing educational efficiency. In recent years, a number of scientific studies have been conducted on the use of digital technologies, virtual laboratories, computer simulations and interactive platforms in the educational process. These studies emphasize that modern technologies activate the educational process and create an opportunity to connect theoretical knowledge with practice. However, the issue of introducing modern technologies into molecular physics on a systematic and methodological basis has not been sufficiently covered. Although the general didactic capabilities of modern technologies in teaching molecular physics have been widely covered in existing scientific works, specific methods of their application in molecular physics teaching, their pedagogical effectiveness and impact on educational outcomes have not been sufficiently studied. Therefore, there is a need to conduct scientifically based research in this area. The purpose of this study is to identify the types of modern educational

technologies and develop ways to effectively use them in the process of teaching molecular physics. To achieve the set goal, the following tasks were set:

- analyze the types of modern educational technologies;
- study the traditional methods used in teaching molecular physics;
- identify the didactic capabilities of virtual laboratories and computer simulations;
- assess the effectiveness of lessons organized on the basis of modern technologies. The

study proposes a methodological model for the use of modern technologies in molecular physics education and scientifically substantiates their impact on the educational process. The results of the study are of practical importance in improving the teaching process of molecular physics in higher educational institutions, organizing classes on the basis of modern technologies, and developing methodological recommendations for professors and teachers.

Literature review: The problem of increasing the effectiveness of education through the full use of modern technologies in teaching molecular physics in higher educational institutions of our republic is scientifically substantiated in the works of such scientists as K.A. Tursunmetov, N. Sadridinov, J.A. Hamidov.

The use of video and animation in teaching molecular physics is considered an important innovative tool for increasing the cognitive and motivational effectiveness of the educational process from a scientific and pedagogical point of view. For example, dynamic 3D animations in teaching the structure of molecules help students fully understand molecules. As a research scientist, I note that such tools are important in describing empirical data. Looking at international experience, the teaching of molecular physics in the educational systems of the USA, Great Britain, Germany, Japan and South Korea is quite rich and technologically advanced. For example, in the US, the Next Generation Science Standards (NGSS) integrate molecular physics with physics and chemistry, but students are given hands-on experience through virtual labs, digital platforms, and partnerships with NASA. In Germany, molecular physics is offered as a separate course in schools, with virtual labs and observational tools available to every student

METHODS:

In this study, a comprehensive methodological approach was used to determine the effectiveness of using modern educational technologies in teaching molecular physics. Theoretical and empirical methods were used in the research process. Theoretical research methods included methods of analyzing, comparing and summarizing scientific and pedagogical literature. Using these methods, traditional and modern technologies used in molecular physics education were analyzed. Pedagogical experimental work, observation, questionnaire and test methods were used as empirical research methods. During the experiment, molecular physics classes in higher educational institutions were organized on the basis of modern technologies, including virtual laboratories, computer simulations and interactive educational platforms.

Experimental work was conducted in control and experimental groups. In the control group, classes were conducted using traditional methods, while in the experimental group, classes were organized using modern technologies. The effectiveness of the learning process was assessed based on the criteria of knowledge level, independent work skills, and learning motivation.

RESULTS. The methodology of teaching molecular physics is to teach observation methods in physics, its connection with other disciplines, teaching planning methods, teaching using modern technologies, and problem-based teaching. The task of this subject is to show students of higher educational institutions the practical value of knowledge in teaching molecular physics, to show the importance of physics in the development of scientific and technical progress,

to help them learn about the improvement of molecular recording devices and the development of modern information technologies in processing the results obtained. List of methods recommended for practice in Uzbekistan:

1. Virtual laboratories - organizing virtual observation lessons using free programs such as Stellarium, Celestia.
2. Mini-projects and research tasks - giving students tasks to observe, analyze, and compile on the topic.
3. Interactive methods - visualization of physical phenomena using 3D simulations, AR (augmented reality) applications.
4. Participation in international online projects - involving students in international projects such as NASA Globe Observer, ESA Astro Pi.
5. Strengthening interdisciplinary integration - organizing joint laboratory exercises between astronomy-physics-informatics.

The results of the conducted pedagogical experiments showed that the use of modern educational technologies in teaching molecular physics significantly increases the effectiveness of education. It was found that the level of mastery of theoretical knowledge of students in the experimental group was higher than that of the control group. The use of computer simulations and virtual laboratories allowed for visual perception of molecular processes and increased the level of students' understanding of abstract concepts. As a result, students developed the skills of independent analysis, drawing conclusions and solving practical problems. The results of the survey showed that students' interest in the subject and their activity in classes increased. Classes organized on the basis of modern technologies increased students' motivation for learning and ensured the interactivity of the educational process. In general, the results of the study confirm that the use of modern technologies in molecular physics education improves the quality of the educational process and serves to improve educational outcomes.

	EVALUATION CRITERIA	CONTROL GROUP (in percent)	EXPERIMENTAL GROUP (in percent)
1	Level of mastery of theoretical knowledge	56%	76%
2	Practical problem-solving skills	52%	72%
3	Level of activity in the lesson	48%	80%
4	Independent working skills	50%	77%
5	Learning motivation	55%	86%

Table 1. Comparison of results of control and experimental groups.

DISCUSSION

Based on the results of the study, the following practical recommendations were developed to improve the teaching process of molecular physics:

1. It is recommended to regularly use virtual laboratories and computer simulations in molecular physics lessons, as they visually and clearly demonstrate complex molecular processes.

2. Combining theoretical classes with interactive educational technologies, including the use of digital presentations, animations, and online platforms, increases student activity in the lesson.

3. When organizing practical and laboratory classes, it is advisable to introduce tasks aimed at independent work based on digital learning resources.

4. Organizing advanced training courses for professors and teachers on the use of modern educational technologies will serve to improve the quality of molecular physics education.

5. It is recommended to use a competency-based approach and diagnostic assessment methods when evaluating lessons organized on the basis of modern technologies.

According to the results of the study, it is advisable to continue scientific research in the following areas:

1. Research the possibilities of artificial intelligence and adaptive learning systems in molecular physics education.

2. Study the impact of lessons organized on the basis of modern technologies on long-term educational outcomes.

3. Determine the pedagogical effectiveness of using virtual laboratories in an integrated manner with real laboratory exercises.

4. Analyze the possibilities of using modern technologies in teaching molecular physics at different educational levels (bachelor's, master's).

5. Scientific substantiation of the issues of forming individual educational trajectories using modern technologies

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, the study focused on determining the pedagogical effectiveness of using modern educational technologies in teaching molecular physics. During the study, the possibilities of improving the quality of education by introducing digital technologies, virtual laboratories, computer simulations and interactive educational platforms into the educational process were analyzed on a scientific basis. The results of pedagogical experimental work showed that classes organized on the basis of modern technologies significantly increase the level of students' mastery of theoretical knowledge, practical problem-solving skills and activity in the lesson. In particular, visual modeling of processes at the molecular level facilitated students' understanding of abstract concepts and served to develop independent and critical thinking skills. Based on the results of the study, it is confirmed that the systematic and targeted use of modern technologies in molecular physics education increases the effectiveness of the educational process, increases student motivation and improves the quality of mastering subjects. The results of this study are of practical importance in improving the methodology of teaching molecular physics in higher education institutions, introducing innovative approaches, and modernizing the educational process. The use of electronic resources is of strategic importance in increasing the effectiveness of students' mastery in teaching molecular physics. This method interests the student, makes him an active participant, provides an individual approach, and serves to consolidate knowledge. Therefore, the systematic and targeted use of electronic learning tools in teaching this subject is a necessary need in the modern education system. The most important requirement for modern lessons today is to use innovative technologies in the lesson process, scientifically substantiate each topic, determine the volume of material taking into account the capabilities of students, determine its complexity,

connect it with previously studied materials, identify tasks for students, enrich the lesson with material and technical equipment, additional visual aids, additionally use information technology tools, and constantly introduce interdisciplinary innovative methods into lessons

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